

Using a Coherent Reflection Model of the Cochlea to Simulate Spontaneous Otoacoustic Emissions in the Presence of Noise

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Abstract. Sounds generated by the inner ear in the absence of external stimuli are called spontaneous otoacoustic emissions (SOAEs). A widely accepted theory for the generation of SOAEs is that of coherent reflection, in which putative inhomogeneities distributed throughout the cochlea are thought to produce coherent reflections at a set of discrete frequencies. Although experimental evidence has mounted for coherent reflection, the influence of physiological noise on coherent reflection models of the cochlea has not been studied. A coherent reflection model is implemented in state space with cochlear roughness being modeled as uncorrelated, additive, spatial perturbation in organ of Corti parameters. Instances of the coherent reflection model are considered in which dense (broad wavenumber) inhomogeneities are replaced by a local region of dense inhomogeneities such that a single SOAE is produced at the characteristic frequency of the local region of dense inhomogeneities. Noise is modeled as internal, uncorrelated, temporal forcing on the basilar membrane. The introduction of noise broadens SOAE peaks, and the presence of noise transforms the amplitude distribution of SOAEs from a bimodal distribution (indicative of an active oscillator) to a unimodal distribution (indicative of filtered white noise). The spectra and amplitude distribution of the coherent reflection models with noise are qualitatively similar to experimental SOAE recordings.

INTRODUCTION

Spontaneous otoacoustic emissions (SOAEs) are generally modeled in two ways: (1) coupled stable sections model (CSS models) [1, 2]; (2) coupled limit cycle oscillators (CLCO models) [3, 4]. In each case, the number of degrees of freedom in each section is up to the discretion of the modeler; for example, the section model can be as simple as just a single lumped mass element representing the basilar membrane (BM) or it can include complex kinematics, such as in the case of the Bowling, Lemons, Meaud model [1]. The key differentiator between CSS and CLCO classes of models is that individual sections of a CSS model are *not* required to be oscillatory (have at least one unstable eigenvalue) for the existence of SOAEs. In contrast, this is *not* true for CLCO models; even in cases, such as the Fruth and Julicher model [4], wherein the control parameter ϵ , which controls the linear stability of each section, is not necessarily positive, SOAEs only occur *when* the control parameter makes some subset of the total number of sections unstable. For SOAEs to be generated in CSS models, by contrast, *roughness* is required. Roughness is introduced into γ , which controls the feedback in the system. Roughness is obtained when the control parameter exhibits broad wavenumber variation in magnitude over part of (or the entirety of) the domain. The theory which governs this mechanism is called coherent reflection, as originally described by Shera in his seminal 2003 paper [5].

For both CSS and CLCO models, internal noise is critical for obtaining realistic values for the quality factor of SOAE peaks; without internal noise, the quality factor predicted by cochlear models is significantly higher than what is observed in mammalian and non-mammalian species [6]. In CLCO models, internal noise has been modeled and studied [3, 4]. The introduction of noise broadens SOAE peaks, decreases their amplitude, and raises the SOAE frequency. Further, amplitude distribution of the SOAE is typically bimodal, indicative of an active system; the introduction of noise should continuously change the bimodal distribution into a unimodal distribution [7, 8, 9]. By contrast, a noisy passive system will exhibit only a unimodal amplitude distribution, which is consistent with filtered noise.

METHODS

The current work is based on the nonlinear transmission line model form Ku and Elliot, which is implemented in state space [2, 10, 11, 12]. Although Ku and Elliot used this model to study SOAE generation, physiological noise was not considered in their work [13]. The micromechanical model, originally conceived of by Neely and Kim [14], is a 2 degree-of-freedom model in which the electromotility is captured phenomenologically through a feedback system

controlled by the activity parameter γ . The sections are coupled together using a 1D traveling wave. The parameters used in the model are adapted from Ku and Elliot's 2009 work on SOAEs in humans [13].

Roughness refers to broad wavenumber variation in the micromechanical control parameter, γ from base to apex. The value of γ for section n is given by

$$\gamma_n = \bar{\gamma}(1 + \sigma\eta_n), \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\gamma}$ is the expected value of γ_n , σ is the standard deviation of the parameter distribution, and η_n is an independently distributed variable sampled from a 0 mean Gaussian distribution with a variance of 1. In the present model, roughness is only applied locally (see Figure 1A and B) so that only a single SOAE is produced, and the parameters of the model were tuned so that only a single linear instability is associated with the model. A value of $\bar{\gamma} = 1$, $\sigma = 5 \times 10^{-2}$ is used in the generation of roughness. The center of the local roughness is at 8.8 mm, and the half length of the roughness is 1.3 mm. The local roughness begins at 7.5mm from the stapes and ends at 10.1mm from the stapes. Over this interval, the best frequency varies from 7 kHz to 4.75 kHz and the wavelength of the traveling wave varies from 0.399 mm to 0.423 mm, suggesting that the region over which roughness is applied is approximately 6.1-6.5 wavelengths.

The noise applied to the BM is white (flat power spectrum) and is introduced as an additive stochastic variable $w(t)$ with zero mean, uncorrelated in space and time, with covariance given by

$$\langle w(x,t)w(x',t') \rangle = 2D_{\text{KE09}}\delta(t-t')\delta(x-x'). \quad (2)$$

The noise is applied to the model mathematically as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_n = \mathbf{A}_n\mathbf{x}_n + \mathbf{B}_n p_n + [0 \ w_n(t) \ 0 \ 0]^T, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{A}_n and \mathbf{B}_n are the micromechanical system matrix and input matrix, respectively, \mathbf{x}_n is the micromechanical state vector for section n for the BM, and $w_n(t)$ is the stochastic forcing on the BM.

Given that the noise is simple (additive and uncorrelated in space and time), it is approximated in the present work (for computational efficiency) through cubic interpolation of an independently identically distributed discrete random variable sampled from a 0 mean Gaussian distribution. Theoretical analysis [15, 16] and numerical experimentation confirmed that the noise is effectively broadband if the noise sampling rate is significantly higher than the highest frequency of interest of the system (we use a noise sampling rate of 100 kHz, which is higher than the maximum characteristic frequency of the model of 20 kHz).

The model was simulated for 180s, with 1s being regarded as the time to reach steady-state. The power spectral density was approximated using the overlap and add method [17]. The output was sampled at 44.1 kHz, and windows of 8s with 93.75% were used, values which are similar to experiments which have been performed on humans [6].

RESULTS

Effect of Noise on the Spectral Properties of the Stapes Velocity

The linear stability diagram is a scatterplot of the eigenvalues of the linearized system, and it provides crucial information regarding the dynamics of the system [2]. The imaginary part of the eigenvalues (ω , plotted on the x-axis) tells us where the frequencies (in radians/s) of the poles of the system are. The real part (σ , plotted on the y-axis), by contrast, tells us information about the damping associated with each of these poles. When a pole has no damping, it has a real part of precisely 0, lying right on the axis. As damping is added to the system, the real part of the eigenvalue becomes more and more negative, heading toward negative infinity; however, if the pole *increases* the value of the real part such that it has a positive real part, then the system becomes unstable and the response of the linear system grows unbounded. Note that the presence of the saturating nonlinearity in the model prevents the response of the nonlinear system in the time domain from growing unbounded, with a limit cycle oscillator forming instead, giving rise to the SOAE in the ear canal.

For a system to be stable, *every* pole must have a negative real part; if even one eigenvalue has a positive real part (such as in the present work), then the system is considered unstable. The frequency of the instability can be converted to location on the BM according to the tonotopic map of the model. This location is towards the apical end of the region with local roughness, as shown in Figure 1. As the amplitude of the roughness grows, the instability of the system grows until an unstable pole emerges in the system.

FIGURE 1. Simulations of SOAEs with noise in a model with local roughness. A and B show the roughness profile. C and D show the spectrum of the stapes velocity for model without noise ($D_{KE09} = 0$) and with noise. In C and D, the black dots correspond to the linear stability diagram, *i.e.*, the real part of the eigenvalues of the state space matrix, σ , are plotted as function of their imaginary part divided by 2π . Panels B and D are identical to panels A and B, except that they focus on a narrower frequency range around the true SOAE peak. The upper horizontal axis in C and D corresponds to the best place given the frequency on the lower axis, as given by the tonotopic map for the Ku and Elliot model.

In the noiseless case in Figure 1C and D, the spectrum is very sharp and has a peak approximately where the unstable eigenvalue is; there is additionally a peak at $2f_0$ (8.27 kHz), where the second harmonic is.

The averaged power spectra of the time domain simulation is shown in Figure 1C and D in three cases with noise has important qualitative and quantitative differences with the noiseless case. There are two distinct types of peaks in this spectra: the *true SOAEs* (the $f=4.135$ kHz tone in Figure 1) and *filtered noise* (the $f=6.175$ kHz tone in Figure 1). Filtered noise is simply noise which is filtered through a passive system mechanical system (*i.e.*, it acts like forcing for the passive system); the lighter the damping (the closer σ gets to the imaginary axis), the more prominent the filtered noise peak is in the spectrum. In contrast with this are true SOAEs, which are associated with linear instabilities in the system. The introduction of noise into the system broadens the true SOAE peak, reduces its amplitude, and increases its frequency. This is precisely what has been observed in CLCO models of the cochlea [3, 4].

Statistical Properties of the Stapes Velocity

The stapes velocity was filtered around the true SOAE at 4.14 kHz and the most prominent filtered noise peak at 6.18 kHz using a 10th order infinite impulse response filter with a bandwidth of 300 Hz. As it can be seen from Figure 2A, B, and E, the true SOAE is bimodal when there is no noise (Figure 2A) and when there is a low amount of noise (Figure 2B and E) present in the system. As the noise in the system grows, the distribution becomes unimodal. Note that when there is a high level of noise present in the system, the contribution from each peak becomes smeared out over the frequency range, causing the response to be highly coupled in the frequency domain. The coupling effect is what is responsible for the artifact observed in the filtered true SOAE distribution at high noise (the bump in the distribution at 0).

By contrast, the filtered noise peak has significantly different qualitative behavior under noise. What is immediately striking is that the peak is always unimodal, as one would expect. A passive 1D oscillator under noise has a Gaussian distribution and this is what is observed (Figure 2E-G). What is perhaps more subtle is that the standard deviation of the stapes velocity grows significantly as noise increases. Inversely, as the noise approaches 0, the standard deviation of the filtered stapes velocity becomes arbitrarily small.

The distinction observed here is precisely what is observed by Talmadge et al. in their 1991 paper on the statistical properties of SOAEs [8].

FIGURE 2. Amplitude distributions of the filtered stapes velocity response under different noise levels. A-D show the distributions associated with the true SOAE. E-G show the distributions associated with the filtered noise. In the noiseless case, there is no filtered noise peak, thus that panel has been omitted for clarity. The columns of the figure align so that identical noise levels are compared (B and E, C and F, D and G).

CONCLUSION

Just as with CLCO models, the introduction of physiological noise into a coherent reflection model of the cochlea is critical for reproducing spectral and statistical results measured in experiments. It is found that introduction of noise into coherent reflection models increases their bandwidth, decreases their amplitude, and increases their frequency. The introduction of noise further excites additional resonant modes within the system which are *not* SOAEs, but rather filtered noise. True SOAEs have bimodal amplitude distributions in the low noise case, but transition to unimodal as the noise saturates the system. In contrast, filtered noise *always* exhibits unimodal statistical behavior.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research was supported by National Institutes of Health (NIH) Grant Nos. R01 DC016114 and National Science Foundation (NSF) grant 2309953.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSIONS

[Christopher Shera]: As you note, the SOAE peak occurs close to but not exactly at the frequency location of the unstable pole (Fig 1D). Do you understand this? (Maybe it has already been noted and explained by Ku et al.)

[Dani Agramonte]: It's not entirely understood why there is discrepancy between the linear instabilities and the SOAE peaks in the nonlinear time domain simulations. In [13], similar findings are obtained and demonstrated in Figure 15. They suggest that "the interactions of LCOs in models with inhomogeneities at all x are less local and therefore more complex." It should be noted that they don't analyze the case of local inhomogeneity in the same way as when there are dense inhomogeneities applied along the entire length of the cochlear model. Further study is required to understand this discrepancy.

[Christopher Shera]: You correctly note that SOAE generation in CSS models requires "roughness". It also requires "reflections from the stapes". If you can control the magnitude and phase of the stapes reflection (R_{stapes}) in the model, it would be interesting to see how adding noise to the value of R_{stapes} affects SOAE spectra (and their intra- and inter-peak FM and AM correlations). I presume that physiological noise in R_{stapes} would have much lower frequency content than the "thermal" type noise you are adding to the BM response.

[Dani Agramonte]: Internal findings within our lab have demonstrated that altering middle ear parameters significantly impact the number of SOAEs (for example Fig. S7 in [1]). A more systemic study is required to more fully understand the impacts of changing these parameters and establishing a physical interpretation of their meaning.

[Ohla Fedoryk]: did you look in the way the peaks were broadened? I am wondering if it is similar to CLCO models where peaks still have "pointy" (their tops are not rounded and mostly having 1-2 points at the peak).

[Dani Agramonte]: We did, although these results are not included in the manuscript. The introduction of noise does indeed broaden SOAE peaks and make them more "rounded" at the top.

[Ohla Fedoryk]: this comment is tied to previous comment about choice of roughness. did you test only this two sets of roughness? is so is there a need on trying different roughness profiles. Also would be nice to see is there a major difference in peak characteristics once it is unimodal compared to bimodal.

[Dani Agramonte]: We tested other roughness profiles but chose the ones which we felt were most representative. We did notice a phenomenological difference between the way that the filtered noise and true SOAEs changed with noise level, but these results are not in the manuscript.